

HYPERBARIC OXYGEN THERAPY AND OBSTACLES IN THE TREATMENT OF CHRONIC WOUNDS IN THE SINGLE HEALTH SYSTEM

Érica de Andrade Alves da Silva¹
(ericaandradesilva12@gmail.com)¹

Leandro Maia Leão²
(leandro-maia-@hotmail.com)²

Carla Gouveia³
Cesmac University Center, Maceió, Alagoas, Brazil^{1,2,3}

Introduction: The Ministry of Health defines wounds as the loss of continuity of the integument, which can be represented not only by the rupture of the skin but also, in more critical cases, the sampling of tendons, muscles and bones. From this perspective, hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBO) has been used to treat wounds since 1622, with the aim of re-establishing normal tissue patterns through the administration of oxygen jets close to 100% pure air, which causes an increase in blood pressure and therefore promotes physiologically therapeutic effects on healing and tissue cell reconstruction. **Objective:** To analyze and describe the relevance of hyperbaric oxygen therapy for the treatment of chronic wounds. **Methodology:** This is an integrative literature review, with a reflexive, descriptive and qualitative analysis. Eight articles were used from the Nursing Database (BDEnf), Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences Literature (Lilacs) and the Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO), using the descriptors "wound healing", "hyperbaric oxygenation" and "nursing" and paired with the boolean AND. **Results:** The characterization of the wounds treated with HBO are those that arise from chronic diseases such as diabetes mellitus, which the patient physiologically has a delay in his recovery if there are no interventions and that most of the time in critical situations end up being subjected to the process of limb amputation, despite its importance in the health sector, there is still a lack of information about the use of this method as a form of therapy, since there is a scarcity of scientific studies in databases on the subject and the absence of government funding for its application in the single health system in a more accessible way for people who need this therapy. **Conclusion:** The HBO technique in the treatment of chronic wounds is viable and has a positive character, especially in situations that are challenging for the health team, for example in cases of complex wounds, such as venous and arterial ulcers, diabetic foot, among others, which more often affect citizens with poorer living conditions and who mostly do not know which treatment to seek, There are obstacles to the applicability of HBO due to the scarcity of hyperbaric chambers in the single health system, which makes the healing of chronic wounds increasingly distant from the reality of the poorest population, and due to the lack of periodic training of the health team for autonomy in the execution of the technique in cases of its applicability in privatized institutions.

Key-Words: Healing. Hyperbaric oxygenation. Nursing.

TYPE OF STUDY: Literature review.

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